

The Effects of Microsoft Teams on Cambodian Undergraduate EFL Students' Academic Achievement

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Abstract

This study investigated the effects of Microsoft Teams on Cambodian undergraduate EFL students' academic achievements at a public university in the northwest of Cambodia and identified the students' opinions toward the use of Microsoft Teams. A quantitative method was utilized to collect both secondary and primary data in this study. 31 undergraduate EFL students, majoring in English Literature were purposely selected to evaluate their academic achievements after employing Microsoft Teams in their classes. The results revealed that students' academic achievement improved after using Microsoft Teams in their learning process. Additionally, the students reported in the survey questions that they had positive opinions toward the use of Microsoft Teams. It can be concluded that using Microsoft Teams in the educational curriculum improves students' academic achievement, makes teaching and learning more efficient, and is a good implementation if educational institutions are able to include Microsoft Teams in other courses at any level of educational programs.

Keywords: *Microsoft Teams, Cambodian undergraduate EFL students, Academic achievement.*

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Introduction

An internet connection has become increasingly important in today's globalization as it plays an essential role in enhancing human activities across various fields, including economic development, cultural exchange, national defense, and many other areas (Fallows, 2004). E-learning, which incorporates technology into teaching, has had a significant impact on the education system in the twenty-first century, as technological advancement has increased (Nguyen & Duong, 2021). Since internet connectivity and technology have been increasing, students have switched to online learning, especially during the spread of COVID-19. Even though COVID-19 has ended, the practices of online learning both in educational institutions and other industries are still present.

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According to Dhawan (2020), online learning is defined as learning experiences in synchronous or asynchronous environments using various devices (e.g., mobile phones, laptops, tablets, etc.) with internet access (Eriyanti, & Oktavia, 2023). Online learning can make the teaching and learning process easier, more innovative, and more student-centered learning. Online education allows students to work at their own pace and in the location that best suits their needs; accessing class materials and submitting work is effortless now because everything is available online (Tran & Nguyen, 2021). Online learning offers accessibility, flexibility, global knowledge, student control over study time, a chance for interaction, cost-effectiveness, better opportunities, and student-centeredness (Seragen, 2020; Candilas, et al., 2023). According to Wagner et al. (2008), online learning assists students through the study of discussion boards, such as forums, email, and chats, which encourage students to engage with each other without fear (Candilas, et al., 2023). As a result, students will consistently access materials, be able to seek help from professors or peers, be able to study at their own pace, utilize their preferred learning devices, and receive timely feedback to reflect on their own learning (Candilas, et al., 2023). Educational institutions found themselves compelled to adopt E-learning methodologies, leveraging a range of visual communication applications, and Microsoft Teams is the most famous application that is suitable for online learning (Sobaih et al., 2021).

Research has shown that Microsoft Teams is a platform that facilitates online teaching and learning, with the potential to enhance the interaction between EFL instructors and their students (Rojabi, 2020). According to AlAdwani and AlFadley (2022), learning through Microsoft Teams is increasing positive student engagement, increasing foreign English language learning, enhancing language abilities, and offering practical assessment. In addition, Alabay (2018) confirmed that the students performed better in their exams when using Microsoft Teams, although they performed poorly on paper in the classroom. Enhancing education with technology like e-learning and modern tools aims to boost student achievement and expand their knowledge to meet educational goals effectively (Al-Shboul, 2024). Many research studies confirmed the effectiveness of Microsoft Teams in terms of teaching and learning; however, the research in Cambodian context on the effects of Microsoft Teams has not been found. Therefore, this study aims to investigate the effects of Microsoft Teams on undergraduate students following these two research questions:

1. What is the effect of Microsoft Teams on undergraduate EFL students' academic achievement?
2. What is the opinion of undergraduate EFL students toward Microsoft Teams?

Technology Assisted Language Learning

Technology Assisted Language Learning (TALL) offers an effective approach to developing strong language proficiency and diverse language abilities, promoting task-based and skill-focused learning among EFL students rather than relying solely on rote memorization (Ahmad, 2016). According to Nawaila et al. (2020), more technology has been used for teaching and learning English over the past three years, reflecting a global trend of integrating technology into schools worldwide.

The integration of technology in language education has been demonstrated to enhance learner motivation and accommodate diverse learning styles, thereby contributing to improved educational outcomes (Shaji & Nagaraj, 2020). The utilization of multimedia resources and interactive platforms provides students with opportunities to engage with the language in more immersive and contextually relevant

environments, thereby facilitating a deeper understanding and promoting the retention of new information (Alemi, 2016; Melkonyan & Matevosyan, 2020). Furthermore, research highlights that the integration of technology into language learning not only enhances student engagement but also promotes personalized learning experiences, thereby enabling educators to effectively address the diverse needs and learning styles of their students (Lin & Chu, 2018; Shaji & Nagaraj, 2020). The importance of technology in this context is highlighted by its ability to provide educators with tools that facilitate differentiated instruction, enabling educators to design learning experiences customized to each student's unique background and preferences. This, in turn, optimizes the language learning process (Lin & Chu, 2018; Melkonyan & Matevosyan, 2020; Shaji & Nagaraj, 2020). In conclusion, Technology Assisted Language Learning (TALL) enhances language acquisition by fostering skill-oriented learning, improving motivation, and accommodating diverse learning styles. Its capacity for personalization and differentiated instruction makes it an essential tool for optimizing educational outcomes in EFL contexts.

Microsoft Teams as Learning Tool

Microsoft Teams is a cloud app digital hub that connects the discussions, meetings, files, and apps together in a single Learning Management System (LMS) (Microsoft, 2018). Moreover, Microsoft allows students and educators from all institutions to sign up for free Microsoft software such as Word, Excel, PowerPoint, OneNote, and Microsoft Teams, as well as other teaching tools, by using a valid school email address (Microsoft, 2020). Buchal and Songsore (2019) stated that Microsoft Teams is an integral component of the Office 365 suite, designed to enhance the features and tools provided by Microsoft SharePoint through its intuitive and user-friendly interface and the platform supports live voice calls, video broadcasts, and interactive chats, fostering seamless communication and collaboration. Furthermore, Microsoft Teams is accessible across various devices, including iOS devices, and windows computers. It can also be used directly via an internet browser. Notably, this application is included in the educational licenses provided to numerous schools and universities, making it a widely authorized tool in academic settings.

In Microsoft Teams, dedicated meeting rooms can be established for conducting meetings and class sessions, where direct video communication is supported, and meeting recordings can be generated. Additionally, resources including media files, digital books, and instructional content can be shared, real-time communication between instructors and students is facilitated, and assessments can be designed and graded electronically by educators (Ismail & Ismail, 2020). The use of the Microsoft Teams facilitated positive interaction in the learning process. This outcome is attributed to the platform's quality, ease of use, and accessible tools, which promoted effective participation between instructors and students while enabling swift feedback exchange (Almondaires et al., 2021). Based on Alameri et al. (2020), the implementation of Microsoft Teams has led to advancements in the teaching-learning process, including more effective assessment and monitoring of student activities and assignments, improved classroom management, and enhanced teacher-student communication. Wichanpricha (2021) stated that the Microsoft Teams was instrumental in enhancing students' motivation to learn, facilitating interaction, and achieving educational goals.

In summary, Microsoft Teams has proven to be an effective platform in education, enhancing interaction, motivation, and participation while supporting assessment, classroom management, and communication between instructors and students.

Previous Studies of Microsoft Teams in Teaching and Learning

The researchers reviewed numerous studies relevant to the scope of the current research. These studies are presented below in chronological order:

AlAdwani and AlFad (2022) studied on Kuwaiti EFL students' opinions of online instruction delivered through Microsoft Teams during the COVID-19 pandemic. The research was conducted using a quantitative method, and the data were collected from 440 EFL students majoring in English at the College of Basic Education in Kuwait using an individual survey with 30 items that focused on three dimensions: interaction, learning, and assessment. The findings showed that the students had neutral opinions regarding online education on the Microsoft Teams. However, the study discovered additional benefits of studying through Microsoft Teams, such as encouraging positive interaction among students, increasing the learning of the foreign English language, enhancing language skills, and providing practical assessment (AlAdwani, & AlFadley, 2022).

Laquindanum (2022) explored undergraduate students' perceptions of Microsoft Teams as a Learning Management System (LMS) for virtual learning. The quantitative method was used and data were collected from 419 students of Western Mindanao State University using a survey questionnaire consisting of 18 items divided into 4 parts: basic functions, assessment, features, and general. Findings suggested that Microsoft Teams is rated as average in effectiveness compared to other online platforms. Students found it useful, simple, and easy to use, especially for its features and assessments. However, a fast internet connection is necessary for optimal performance. Additionally, there are no significant differences in perceived effectiveness based on gender or year level.

Tran & Nguyen (2021) evaluated the effectiveness of online teaching with the Microsoft Teams application with fifty non-English students at the University of Education and the University of Da Nang in Vietnam. The study conducted by using quantitative method with survey questions. The findings of the study revealed that the students gave positive feedback after using Microsoft Teams in their last semester. In addition, Microsoft Teams is not only a well-known platform for learning, but also a good platform for teaching, and the author also suggested that schools or institutions should continue to promote the efficient use of Microsoft Teams for teaching and helping students' learning at home.

Bsharat and Behak (2020) conducted a study to examine the effectiveness of the Microsoft Teams application in enhancing English language teaching and learning during the COVID-19 pandemic, as perceived by English teachers in Jenin City. Quantitative method was used in this study by using questionnaire consisted of 15 items developed by the researchers based on their experiences and the available literature. There were 25 English language teachers selected from the community of teachers. As a result, the instructors felt that the most important aspect of Microsoft Teams was that students would share files and content, and there are options for screen sharing that provide teachers the flexibility to show anything they want in the classroom.

Rojabi (2020) explored EFL students' perceptions of online learning via Microsoft Teams at University level in Indonesia. The data were collected from 28 students online using a questionnaire. The study revealed that the students had a positive opinion of the learning environment in an online class and it improved their skills to

work effectively with others via Microsoft Teams. However, it was difficult to make the interaction between teacher and students.

Alabay (2018) investigated classroom experiences with Microsoft Teams for foreign language teaching. The study was conducted using quantitative approach and 21 students in pre-class were purposively selected for the study. The data was gathered through students' exam papers. The finding of the study revealed that after taking the exam, the students got better scores when using Microsoft Teams compared to the scores on exam paper in the classroom.

In conclusion, the majority of the studies primarily focused on enhancing students' language learning skills, interaction, assessment processes, functionality, and feedback through the use of Microsoft Teams. However, limited attention has been given to its impact on learning achievement.

Materials and Methods

This study utilized a quantitative research method in order to attain greater knowledge and understanding of the students' opinions using Microsoft Teams. Babbie (2013) emphasizes the importance of quantitative methods in social research, highlighting their role in producing objective, reliable, and generalizable findings. He discusses how structured research designs and statistical analyses contribute to the validity and replicability of studies, making quantitative research essential for testing hypotheses and establishing patterns within social phenomena. According to Campbell et al. (2020) purposive sampling improves the accuracy of the study and the reliability of the data and outcomes by better matching the sample to the research's goals and objectives (Ager-Sharrieff, 2022). Through the implementation of a purposive sampling technique, the participants consisted of 31 undergraduate students majoring in English Literature. Table 1 shows the year of the study and the gender of the participants in this study. The students were from the second year and third year, and most of the participants were female students 71.4%, while there were only 28.6% of males and their ages ranged from 18 to 25 years old. The demographic details of the participants are outlined in the tables provided below.

Table 1. Year of the Study and Gender of Participants

	Second year	Third year	Male	Female
Percentage	48.39%	51.61%	28.6%	71.4%

Research Instruments

The present study utilized both secondary and primary data. The secondary data was the students' achievement in online and offline classes, two sets of grade point averages from all subjects. One set was from an offline class on campus, and another was from an online class using Microsoft Teams.

Additionally, the primary data was the questionnaire that was adapted and modified from AlAdwani and AlFadle (2022) to examine students' opinions toward Microsoft Teams and was made on an online platform called Google Forms with a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 = Strongly disagree to 5 = Strongly agree.

Data Collection

Both secondary and primary data were collected. Assisted by the head of the English Department of the Institute of Foreign Languages, two sets of grade point averages of all subjects were collected before the questionnaire was administered.

After the students signed the informed consent form, questionnaires were distributed to students via Telegram and it took about 15 minutes to complete two parts of the questionnaire: the first part included 5 items gathering students' personal information, while the second part consisted of 15 items evaluating students' opinions towards the use of Microsoft Teams.

Data Analysis

Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 25 was used to analyze descriptive statistics and Paired-Sample T-Test. Paired-Sample T-Test analyzed on the set of the scores before and after using Microsoft Teams as a learning tool. Descriptive statistics were used to find out the students' opinions on Microsoft Teams. According to Laquindanum (2022), the scale below provides a structured framework for interpreting students' responses, ranging from strong disagreement to strong agreement, ensuring clarity in data analysis. Interpretation Scale:

- 1.0 – 1.79: Strongly Disagree
- 1.80 – 2.59: Disagree
- 2.60 – 3.39: Neutral
- 3.40 – 4.19: Agree
- 4.20 – 5.00: Strongly Agree

Results and Discussion

The Effects of Microsoft Teams on Students' Academic Achievement

Table 2 illustrated mean scores of Paired-Sample T-Test of students' GPA before and after using Microsoft Teams. The mean difference of GPA before and after was 0.59 and p value was lower than 0.05. As a result, the GPA score before and after using Microsoft Teams varied significantly. It was possible to draw the conclusion that using Microsoft Teams as learning tool improved the students' academic achievement.

Table 2. Year of the Study and Gender of Participants

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
				Lower	Upper			
GPA before- GPA after	0.59	0.46	0.08	0.42	0.76	7.14	30	0.00

Students' Opinions toward Microsoft Teams

Table 3 illustrated students' opinions toward the use of Microsoft Teams in terms of academic achievement.

The result demonstrated the students' positive opinion towards Microsoft Teams with overall mean 3.44 (M=3.44). According to the mean score calculated for each item on the questionnaire, nine of the 15 defined items received positive response, while the remaining six received a neutral response. Among these are items (1, 2, and 15) which ranged between (3.61-3.90) were the highest mean in the study. The students concurred that the instructional materials made available on Microsoft Teams, including videos, PowerPoint presentations, articles, and assignments, significantly contributed to their comprehension of the course content. Furthermore, engagement in online activities and discussions via Microsoft Teams fostered their motivation to study. Moreover, the students would recommend Microsoft Teams to other learners to experience too.

Furthermore, the students also rated positively on items (3, 6 and 10), the mean ranged between 3.48-3.54. The students stated that when using Microsoft Teams would save both money and time, helping to shorten the duration needed for taking quizzes and tests. Besides, they really satisfied with Microsoft Teams as a learning assistance. In addition, items (8, 11 and 12) got exactly the same mean 3.45. Students agreed that Microsoft Teams was very easy when submitting homework and assignments. The students accepted that they do better on online assessments through Microsoft Teams compared to traditional paper assessments while using the helpful function such as file or note.

Items 4, 5, and 14, which fall within the range of 3.29 to 3.35, the students felt neutral even though the students recognize some benefits of Microsoft Teams, they remain uncertain about its role in enhancing language skills and improving learning effectiveness. Additionally, students are unsure whether they can complete assessments more efficiently and effectively on Microsoft Teams compared to traditional classroom-based assessments. On the other hand, items (7, 9 and 13) which ranged between 3.16-3.25 were the lowest mean showed the hesitation of students about interaction between lecturer and students while learning through Microsoft Teams as well as they feel uncomfortable when answering question. The students are still exploring the extent to which they may require assistance from others when completing online assessments through Microsoft Teams. Overall, the findings highlight that the students have a favourable perception of Microsoft Teams.

Table 3. Students' Opinions toward Microsoft Teams

N ^o	Statements	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1	The posted materials (videos, PowerPoint files, articles, assignments) on Microsoft Teams helped me understand the course content.	3.90	0.53	Agree
2	Online activities and discussions through Microsoft Teams motivated me to learn the course material	3.61	0.49	Agree
3	Online learning through Microsoft Teams saves money and time.	3.51	0.99	Agree
4	Online learning through Microsoft teams improves my language skills.	3.35	0.70	Neutral
5	Online learning through Microsoft Teams increases the effectiveness of my learning.	3.29	0.73	Neutral
6	I am satisfied with the use of the Microsoft Teams for learning assistance.	3.48	0.72	Agree

7	Online learning through Microsoft Teams makes interaction and communication easier between lecturers and students.	3.16	0.86	Neutral
8	Online learning through Microsoft Teams is convenient to use, especially with submitting homework and assignments.	3.45	0.85	Agree
9	I feel comfortable in answering questions in an online class through Microsoft Teams.	3.25	0.92	Neutral
10	Online assessments (Tests and quizzes) through Microsoft Teams reduces the amount of time given for taking quizzes and tests.	3.54	0.72	Agree
11	I do better on online assessments through Microsoft Teams compared to traditional paper assessments.	3.45	0.62	Agree
12	During online assessments through Microsoft Teams, I use helpful functions such as note and file.	3.45	0.76	Agree
13	During online assessments through Microsoft Teams, I do not need help from another person.	3.22	0.76	Neutral
14	During online assessments through Microsoft Teams, I do faster and better than in classroom.	3.32	0.74	Neutral
15	I would like to recommend Microsoft Teams to other learners to experience.	3.67	0.70	Agree
	Overall	3.44	0.74	Agree

The Effects of Microsoft Teams towards Undergraduate EFL Students' Academic Achievement

The findings indicated that using Microsoft Teams had a positive impact on undergraduate students' learning achievement. This result aligned with the study of Alabay (2018); Alameri et al. (2020); Keerio et al. (2022) and Ayman et al. (2024) that students perceived Microsoft Teams as beneficial for enhancing their knowledge, self-study habits, work efficiency, and the quality of assignments and get higher examination score.

Students' Opinion towards the Use of Microsoft Teams

The results of the current study revealed that the students had a positive attitude toward Microsoft Teams on learning demission. In this study, students reported that the materials provided on Microsoft Teams such as videos, PowerPoint presentations, articles, and assignments were highly effective in helping them understand the course content, indicating that the platform's features were beneficial. This result in lined with the previous research, which found that the students were assisted in accessing information and learning materials (Sobaih et al., 2021). In addition, Bsharat & Behak (2020) and Tran & Nguyen (2021), found that Microsoft Teams enabled students to share files and share content, including screen sharing options that allowed teachers to display what they chose during the class. Besides, the students were encouraged to learn the course material because the teachers provided online activities and discussion in Microsoft Teams during the online class.

In addition, the present study revealed that the interaction between students and students, students and lecturers when using Microsoft Teams got a neutral rate in the questionnaire, which means that the students still unsure about the interaction between teachers and students when using Microsoft Teams. The result supports the previous study, Rojabi (2020), who discovered that students disagreed that online teaching makes the interaction between teachers and students easier. Alahmadi and Alraddadi

(2020), on the other hand, discovered that Saudi EFL students in virtual classrooms interacted and communicated well with one another, which is inconsistent with this result.

More importantly, the students admitted that they do better when there is an assessment through Microsoft Teams compared to paper assessment. This outcome was consistent with Laquindanum (2022), who claimed that learners found online assessments more manageable as they experienced less pressure compared to face-to-face assessments. Due to less pressures related to assessment compared to in-person evaluation, the learners found it easier. Compared to in-class assessments, where the teacher is present, the online exam was easier to access since it allowed students to use resources like textbooks or other students' assistance during the test. Additionally, it is not a major issue; this could be resolved in the future by improving the function.

Conclusion

The present study investigated the effects of Microsoft Teams on EFL students' academic achievement and also examined their opinion towards this implementation. The results clearly indicate that Microsoft Teams had a positive impact and was appreciated by all students. Microsoft Teams is an effective platform for educational purposes because of its high quality, accessibility, and functionalities. The tool, according to the students, was extremely helpful for encouraging interactive learning and boosting academic achievement. It is recommended that we keep promoting the efficient use of Microsoft Teams for teaching by using traditional and virtual classrooms, even if schools and colleges have gone back to the traditional method of instruction since the whole country and the world have completely recovered from the COVID-19 incident. Since we could not guarantee that COVID-19 or other diseases will occur again, Microsoft Teams should be utilized as a supporting instrument to help organize students' learning in and outside classroom. This will allow both teacher and students to be familiar to the programmed and make it easier to use in the future.

The findings of the present study demonstrate that Microsoft Teams has significantly enhanced students' learning outcomes. Moreover, the results raised several compelling questions and generated valuable recommendations for pedagogical practices and future research:

1. Future investigations may prioritize examining the efficacy of Microsoft Teams through observational research, such as employing a mixed-methods research design, to generate more conclusive evidence supporting the advantages of this online learning platform.
2. Researchers may also consider utilizing cross-sectional research to critically assess the benefits and limitations of Microsoft Teams while identifying potential challenges or barriers encountered by users.
3. Subsequent studies could explore diverse educational contexts, including varying school levels, proficiency levels, age groups, and subject areas (e.g., pure science disciplines). Such investigations would provide opportunities to evaluate whether the platform remains effective across different student demographics and academic domains

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